

Research ethics and bioethics expert Mani Moor (he/him)

"My training in identifying potential risks and harms of research helps me thrive while engaging with difficult questions about ethical practices in different stages of research"

Bio

For the past five years Mani has worked as an interim ethics expert in clinical and research settings, a dynamic role with interdisciplinary scope. As an ethicist, he consults simultaneously on numerous projects where scientific and technological development may affect humans, animals, or the environment. He ensures that research delivers more benefit than harm, is conducted in a respectful and socially responsible manner, and follows ethical codes and legal guidelines. In addition, he conducts and sometimes supervises research projects focused on research ethics and integrity, bioethics, technology ethics, and improving codes of conduct. Through these projects he extends his network and enhances his knowledge of ethical issues in various contexts. He participates regularly in IRB and ethics committee meetings. In addition to guest lecturing on research ethics and integrity to cohorts in different career stages, he also contributes to and submits grant applications. Most of his time is spent on writing original text or reviewing text/protocols written by others with a view to minimize harm and improve research excellence.

Education: PhD in Ethics
Years of experience: 5
Work location: Mostly remote work on his laptop but occasionally has in-person meetings

Goals

- Develop and teach ethics programs to students and researchers from different disciplines
- Conduct research on various ethical aspects of research (e.g., bias, respect for subjects)
- Serve on ethics committees and consult on different projects
- Develop and improve policies about conducting research

Software attitude & use

- Feels confident about learning and using a range of different programs
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Box, Slack, Zoom, WebEx, Teams; Zotero, EndNote
- Specialized resources include survey and analysis software (e.g., REDCap, Qualtrics, Dedoose, NVivo) and bibliographic resources (e.g., Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science)

Outputs

- Peer-reviewed manuscripts, preprints, poster presentations
- IRB applications and research grants

Pain Points

- Over-committed and unable to "switch off" or attend all meetings
- Ever-changing computer settings in the name of security or privacy
- Insufficient technical support
- Formatting challenges with reference management software
- Lack of workforce diversity in some academic contexts and in leadership

Motivators

- Engage with and influence ethics discussions
- Explore questions about research subjects and their rights, as well as the ethics of using big data and AI technologies
- Abolish disparities in research based on gender, race, and ethnicity
- Provide ethical insights on as many projects as possible
- Achieve a rewarding and productive career in biomedicine as a member of a collaborative team

Wants/Needs

- Access to literature and relevant sources
- IT capacity to facilitate working on different projects
- More financial/technical/human resources for research
- Help with grant submission such as budgeting and other non-scientific documentation
- Organizational support for personal development

Professional Development

Mani is working toward becoming an executive member of the ethics and bioethics committees

Mani is pursuing a professional track to secure a permanent position

Mani maximizes continuing education opportunities provided by his institution to gain additional training and experience in bioethics, statistics, research communications, and leadership training